

Strategies to Enhance Writing Skills

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Abstract

Writing is a crucial linguistic ability that holds significance not just for students but also for individuals in various professions. Given the significance of writing as a means of communication, it is crucial to impart effective writing skills to individuals. Without a fundamental comprehension of the principles of effective writing, it is challenging, if not unattainable, to produce high-quality written work. Efficient writing articulates the writer's intended message with clarity and simplicity. Conversely, poor writing is inelegant and distracts the reader. The primary objective of this article is to examine the process of writing and effective ways to instruct English language learners in writing skills.

Keywords: writing skills, rules of writing, clarity, teaching strategy, linguistic ability etc.

Introduction

I. GENERAL STRATEGY FOR WRITING SKILL

Writing is a complex and multifaceted process. The process referred to is a systematic sequence of actions that result in a meticulously planned, efficiently structured, and technically accurate written work, such as a historical research paper or a job application letter. Writing is a procedural activity that should adhere to the following procedures.

Prewriting refers to the initial stage of preparing to write.

- Writing: creating a preliminary or initial version.
- Revising: improving the initial draft.
- Editing refers to the process of correcting errors or faults.
- Rewriting refers to the act of duplicating the initial version.

Planning What to Write:

Strategizing is the initial phase of all our endeavours, be it academic or otherwise. Lack of proper planning might fail in any task. Before commencing any writing, it is crucial to establish a well-structured plan that is effective. Before commencing the writing process, a learner must strategize and outline their thoughts. Neglecting to do so may result in an inability to effectively convey ideas. (Alo and Ogunsiji, 2004, p. 248).

During the planning phase, the writer must select a topic that aligns with their objective and captivates their interest. In addition to selecting a captivating topic, the writer must also consider their target audience. The writer must consider their relationship with the intended audience as a top priority.

Choosing and Narrowing a topic

At times, instead of the instructor assigning a topic, the learner should be motivated to select a topic of their preference. Multiple factors need to be considered in this procedure. Before proceeding, the writer must ensure that they possess a sufficient level of interest in the chosen topic. Next, we have the possibility of finding enough amount of resources on the selected subject. Collecting essential material, such as conducting interviews and making personal observations, is crucial for writers (Adegbija, 1989, P.262). Additionally, engaging in discussions with peers about the topic matter is as significant. Once a topic has been chosen, it is imperative to narrow it down to attain a more precise focus. The students' struggle to refine their themes to achieve a pertinent and more precise focus is a significant challenge they face, particularly when choosing research topics for lengthy essays.

Brainstorming

After choosing a topic, the writer must produce ideas related to that particular subject. Brainstorming involves vigorously exploring one's mind until original and innovative ideas start to emerge effortlessly. The process involves evaluating the selected matter, analysing it, scrutinising its different aspects, and even contemplating the perspectives of others. During the brainstorming process, learners rapidly produce multiple ideas before carefully evaluating a subset of them. Brainstorming enables us to contemplate the matter, quickly record every idea that comes to mind, and eventually distinguish between ideas to separate the relevant ones from the irrelevant ones.

Reading Passage and Note-Making

To write with effectiveness and efficiency, a writer must engage in considerable reading to get pertinent information on the given topic. Information can be found on the internet, as well as in textbooks and publications. While engaging in the process of reading, learners should actively and attentively absorb varied information and simultaneously make important annotations. Notes provide users with a summary of the texts they have reviewed. Therefore, it is essential that the notes are succinct, precise, and well-structured.

Preparing an outline

Thorough preparation is essential for achieving success and effectiveness in writing. An outline is an essential tool in the initial stages of writing to achieve the intended goal. Before commencing the actual writing process, it is important to engage in the preparation of an outline (Alo & Ogunsiji 2004, P.253). It serves as a structural foundation for the essay, ensuring its coherence and focus. There are two styles of outlining: Scratch or Informal Outline and Formal Outline.

Informal-Outline

A scratch outline is a concise list of details that are created via brainstorming and consists of words or phrases. Before commencing the writing process, it is advisable to make a brief note of the key points, thoughts, and ideas that will be elaborated upon to accomplish the objective of the writing task. Before commencing the writing process, ideas or points are developed through the act of reflection and brainstorming. Once the concepts have been recorded, the learner should arrange them coherently and systematically. In essence, this method of organising information reveals the main ideas and subideas and consequently acts as a practical tool for the writer.

Formal-Outline

This visual representation illustrates the hierarchical structure and the comparative significance of ideas. The method employed is the conventional practice of utilising indented letters and digits. (Chinwe and Ifeyinwa , 2011 p. 58. A formal outline consists of complete phrases, any of which can be used as the central idea of a paragraph. However, the latter does not include complete phrases.

Drafting

The process of creating a document consists of a series of sequential steps. This is because it necessitates the process of composing the initial draft, making revisions and proofreading it, and subsequently producing the updated or final draft. Drafting involves recording our impromptu thoughts and ideas about a specific matter. During the initial drafting process, the student should not be concerned with meticulous grammar and spelling. These specific aspects can be attended to at a later stage. When composing the initial draft, relinquish all the ideas that the student has been nurturing. Consequently, it is expected that one should write in a smooth and unrestricted manner. The previously mentioned notes and outline in this section are valuable tools for creating the initial draft. Therefore, the student should consult them during the writing process.

Process of Revising

Revision refers to the act of making alterations to enhance both the substance and manner of an essay (Kathleen 2003, p. 156). Revision is essential for all writing assignments since it can significantly impact the extent to which a paper achieves its objective and effectively communicates your ideas to the target readership. Undertaking a thorough revision, especially one that is complete, can be a formidable task. However, it is highly beneficial as it enhances the overall quality of the essay. Revision is a crucial aspect of the writing process since it allows for the incorporation, removal, reorganisation, or rewording of ideas with each iteration. Revision in the writing process is not only limited to fixing grammatical and mechanical errors, but it can also include making changes to important parts of the essay by adding, eliminating, or rearranging them.

Editing

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Frequently, students see papers with amazing ideas that eventually prove unsuccessful, especially when their sentences lack clarity and precision or when their choice of words conveys a wrong tone and diction. To produce high-quality writing, it is essential to meticulously revise the work by carefully examining each phrase and linguistic element to guarantee that it effectively and accurately communicates the intended idea in a captivating way. The goal of editing is to improve the edited text by using concise, accurate phrases, impactful word choices, and a suitable style. It is crucial to keep in mind that revising and editing are the last stages in the writing process, thus deserving careful attention.

Preparing the Final-Draft

Once the first document has been edited and amended, the new portion must be formally drafted. There is still potential for further growth at this stage. Regardless of the quality of the initial essay draft, it can always be enhanced, particularly during the revision phase. When editing the work, it is important to focus on any casual problems in spelling, punctuation, grammar, logic, and style. If the learner is utilising a word processor or computer, he should produce a pristine hard copy of the essay just for proofreading. Avoid using a copy that has already been marked with annotations or the one shown on a computer screen. Producing a pristine duplicate can significantly enhance the efficiency of reviewing and editing.

Documentation

It is crucial to include footnotes, endnotes, and internal citations when documenting our writing in academic contexts. Effective writing cannot be accomplished in isolation. When employed proficiently, including the concepts of other authors that are pertinent to a student's work in some capacity can function as a foundation for their ideas and enhance the quality of their work. When incorporating the concepts or thoughts of others into one's work, regardless of the medium, the learner must demonstrate integrity by properly acknowledging the source. It is imperative to include proper citations for all sources referenced in an essay or paper, either inside the text or in the bibliography at the end. A footnote is commonly positioned at the bottom of the page where the reference is mentioned, but an endnote is typically placed at the end of the paper or chapter. The formats for footnotes and bibliographies vary across different academic disciplines. It is imperative to ascertain the prevailing standard procedure in the specific field. Once the essay has been rewritten, reread, and checked for any kind of problems, such as typographical and keyboarding mistakes, it should be presented in a suitable manuscript format.

2. SPECIFIC STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING WRITING

As academic or professional writers, one must possess a strong command of these strategies to differentiate ourselves in our writing pursuits. The following content explores several micro-strategies that have an impact on the end product, specifically the text.

Sentence construction

Proficient writing also requires the utilisation of proficient sentences. Effective sentences consist of four fundamental aspects. Firstly, sentences must be accurate and succinct. Secondly, they should exhibit variety and avoid uniformity in structure. Lastly, they should possess parallel features and components. Finally, sentences must include strong and powerful active verbs (Kathleen 2003, P. 181). Concise phrases convey their intended message with the fewest possible words. Kathleen provided the following suggestions for attaining brevity in sentences during the process of writing:

a. Eliminate wordy phrases: This entails removing phrases that contribute little or nothing to the meaning of a sentence, such as "Another revolution in the transformation of herbs will come shortly."

This phrase is too verbose. Since the initial phrase does not provide any meaningful information to the statement, it should be removed and the sentence should be rephrased as: "Another revolution in herbal transformation is about to happen."

b. Eliminate Repetition: Redundancy occurs when unnecessary repetition of words or concepts takes place. Redundant phrases involve the repetition of a statement or idea using either identical words or alternative words that convey the same meaning. An instance of redundancy can be observed in the sentence "Choosing law as a career would result in stable, satisfying work" as it repeats the same concept or notion.

The original sentence can be revised as: "Pursuing a career in law guarantees a consistent and fulfilling occupation." By eliminating unnecessary repetition in the second statement, we have eradicated redundancy.

c. Remove unnecessary sentence introductions: Some introductory statements or words complicate the beginning of a sentence. These holes should be eradicated from our sentence patterns, for example, in the line "I think that every cybercafé should ensure the safety of its customers." A more suitable rephrasing of the text might be "Every cybercafé should ensure the security of its patrons."

d. Remove unnecessary adverbs: Adverbs that serve no purpose can impede the flow of writing. Adverbs such as unbelievably, really, so, too, etc. do not significantly enhance or contribute to the meaning of a sentence when they are employed to intensify it. Alternatively, they occasionally weaken the words they modify. As an illustration, the athlete was elated upon discovering that he emerged victorious in the race. This can be written as "Upon learning of his victory in the race, the athlete experienced an overwhelming sense of joy."

e. Eliminate redundant phrases and clauses: The presence of multiple phrases or clauses in sentences might make it difficult for readers to identify and understand the main concept. It is advisable to minimise the use of the following example in our writing: "The grievances expressed by students on campus compelled the vice chancellor to establish additional worship centres within the school." The student's objections prompted the vice chancellor to construct additional worship centres.

f. Alternating our sentences

Diversity is essential in life; a student should utilise a range of sentence forms when writing. To attain diversity in the ultimate composition, it is necessary to combine simple sentences with compound, complex, and compound-complex sentences. Furthermore, the length of sentences has specific impacts on the quality of writing. When modifying the sentence structures in writing, it is important to additionally diversify their lengths. Short sentences are concise and forceful. They propel ideas forward quickly, creating an essay at a fast pace (Kathleen 2003, P.187). Modifying sentence structures is crucial while composing written work. Put simply, the student must alter the arrangement of limiting modifiers to change the pattern or structure of the sentences. This significantly improves the efficacy of our writing.

g. Parallelism in the Sentence Structure

Parallelism is necessary to achieve equilibrium among words, phrases, and clauses. Effective utilisation of parallelism enhances the coherence of phrases, hence facilitating comprehension. For instance, consider the line "The girl is tall, possesses a slender physique, and exudes a delightful sense of humour."

A possible rephrasing of this statement could be: "The young woman possesses a tall stature, slender physique, and a captivating sense of humour."

The second or updated iteration facilitates a more seamless flow of our thoughts and enhances comprehensibility.

h. The use of robust and dynamic verbs

For the writing to be effective, the learners must utilise strong and energetic verbs. Powerful and active verbs enhance the quality of our work. This is in contrast to linking verbs, which can make the writing dull, such as

First Sentence: Upon sighting the lion, the young individual displayed a visage filled with trepidation.

Second Sentence: The child experienced intense fear and tightly held onto his father upon seeing the lion.

Passive: The reward was awarded to the athlete.

Active: The athlete received the reward.

The impact of the forceful and dynamic verbs in the second set of words in each case is evident. The behaviours depicted in the second set of sentences in each case are not only vivid but also energetic.

Suitableness of Tone and Word Selection

Effective writing relies heavily on the careful choice of tone and vocabulary. Tone encompasses the writer's disposition towards the audience and their emotional stance on the selected matter. One's intended tone should be reflected in the choice of words. Kathleen

identifies three dominant degrees of diction. These items are considered formal, widely accepted, and suitable for casual occasions. The formal level is characterised by a serious and imposing atmosphere. The text is often written in the third person and consists of long phrases and vocabulary with several syllables, but it does not use contractions. The piece maintains a consistent and regular tempo, characterised by a distant and authoritative timbre.

Periodicals and newspapers commonly employ popular or casual language. The tone might be described as predominantly colloquial and personal. It is distinguished by contractions and shorter, less varied sentences. Everyday speech and discussion utilise informal language or colloquial terms. The language used is informal, characterised by colloquialisms and occasional use of slang and abbreviations. Fragmented phrases including first and second-person pronouns are indicative of informal language. Except for direct citations and discussion, this style should be ignored in essays and academic writing.

Appropriate Application of Imagery

Regardless of whether the subject matter is tangible or conceptual, the reader generates mental visualisations within their mind. To captivate and sustain readers' interest in any written work, it is essential to employ vivid imagery and symbolism when conveying ideas. Effective utilisation of imagery enhances the writing, imbuing it with vibrancy.

The Application of Figurative Language

Figurative language extends beyond the figures of speech seen in literary works. The phrase is used to refer to any instance where language is used indirectly in a way that is imaginative or creative. Most studies consider the use of figures of speech, such as metaphor or simile, idioms, and proverbs, to be a linguistic metaphor. When employing such linguistic strategies to evaluate our service, especially in essays or other forms of scholarly writing, they exert a distinct impact on the reader. Utilising metaphorical language effectively, especially in academic writing jobs, is worthwhile to differentiate our works from others.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF PARAGRAPHS

Lexemes conjoin to make phrases, which in turn combine to form clauses. These clauses then provide a diverse range of sentence nuances, and when combined, they produce stretches of speech. Proficiency is required to navigate the various possibilities that arise from the combination of words at both the individual and larger discourse levels. To organise paragraphs, which consist of extended pieces of text, it is essential to possess the skill of generating suitable sentences, particularly in a range of different structures. Proficiency in paragraph development is crucial for both professional and academic writing tasks. Within this section, we will analyse the relationship between paragraphs and their corresponding sentences. A paragraph is a cohesive unit of sentences centred around a singular topic sentence (Alo and Ogunsiji 2003, P.258). In the context of language analysis, a paragraph can be regarded as a higher-level unit compared to a sentence. In his work, Egbe (1996, p.51) outlined the many

components of a paragraph, which include: a) composite elements inside the paragraph; b) inter-sentential connections; c) the introductory part of the paragraph; d) the middle portion that contains examples and explanations; and e) the concluding part of the paragraph. Egbe suggests that additional factors to evaluate are the smooth transition between paragraphs, the arrangement of paragraphs in a lengthy piece of writing, and the comprehension of the paragraph's purpose within the text.

A network of relationships can be identified within a piece of discourse. For example, there are interactions between individual words that lead to the creation of phrases, and linkages between clauses that lead to the building of complex sentences. A comprehensive comprehension of these several levels of relationships is essential for crafting a robust paragraph and for producing impactful writing. When correctly managed, the components of vocabulary and sentence structures, agreement between phrases and clauses, sequential organisation of sentences, and semantic connections within paragraphs enhance the understanding of a paragraph. (Egbe, 1996, page 55)

Egbe says that achieving efficient and effective communication requires the appropriate addressing of all these issues.

The Organization of a Paragraph

When analysing the structure of a paragraph, we are referring to the constituent components that are typically linked to the paragraph as a cohesive unit. The components encompassed in this are the introductory statement and its elaboration, the presentation of concepts, and the final remarks. If there had been more space available, each section would have been thoroughly examined and supported with illustrative examples. The topic sentence emphasises the main concept of the paragraph. All other aspects are centred around that. The placement of the item can be at the start, middle, or conclusion of a paragraph. If the purpose statement is positioned at the start of the paragraph, it should be succinctly clarified before being further elaborated. Elaboration is crucial in constructing a paragraph since it provides necessary support. Illustrative instances, manifestations, or narratives might be employed to bolster the main idea. This form of assistance facilitates the efficient formation of paragraphs.

Every paragraph of the essay must be devoid of misspellings and grammatical errors. It is important to ensure that each paragraph includes the necessary linking or cohesion devices. Using appropriate linking techniques in a paragraph enhances both the cohesiveness and coherence of the paragraph, which are essential aspects not only of the paragraph itself but also of the overall essay.

Characteristics of a Paragraph

A paragraph is characterised by its coherence, which refers to the logical and organised flow of ideas inside the paragraph. It is also marked by emphasis, which highlights the main points or ideas of the paragraph. Additionally, cohesion is an important aspect of a paragraph, ensuring that the sentences are connected and related to each other. These three elements are essential for a paragraph to be effective. A paragraph demonstrates unity when each of its

phrases directly reinforces the topic sentence. A paragraph lacking coherence is characterised by the inclusion of one or two sentences that fail to directly relate to the topic sentence. Coherence is another essential element of a paragraph. Syntax focuses on the cohesive integration of different elements inside phrases. Focus or emphasis, conversely, pertains to the ability of a sentence's structure to accentuate its main argument.

Inter-sentence Connections

The logical coherence of phrases inside a paragraph is equally crucial when evaluating the efficiency of sentences in a particular essay. Inter-sentential interconnections in a paragraph pertain to the syntactic and semantic associations among sentences. To accomplish this goal, it is imperative to examine not only the limitations imposed by English phraseological constraints, but also the restrictions on the expression of concepts in the language (Egbe 1996, P.56). Egbe categorises how an individual's thoughts are presented in a text as follows: a) The logical connection between cause and effect, or action and reaction; b) The organisation of events using a coherent parameter, such as chronology or geographical location, in a way that allows for the recognition of the underlying logic; and c) The preservation of a natural progression of ideas. Egbe says that all of these methods are highly valuable, as they not only aid in establishing the sequence of words but also in determining the logical progression of information.

4. WRITING PARAGRAPHS WITH EFFECTIVENESS

Mastery of grammar and punctuation alone is inadequate for composing impactful paragraphs. The proficiency to construct well-elaborated supporting paragraphs inside the body of an essay is of utmost importance in this context. A comprehensive supporting paragraph comprises a topic sentence along with definitions, explanations, examples, or other pertinent information that bolsters the thesis of the essay. Furthermore, it is essential to employ transitions and repeats to demonstrate the correlation between ideas (Kathleen 2003, P.126). A paragraph that possesses the mentioned characteristics is not only effective but also exhibits a high level of development. In contrast, a poorly constructed paragraph consists primarily of subjective statements. There is a lack of evidence to substantiate these opinions. The text does not have well-defined topic sentences and cohesive, elaborated supporting elements, transitions, and repetitions that effectively illustrate the connection between the ideas.

The Inter-paragraph Transition

The occurrence of transitioning from one paragraph to the next is frequent in well-structured writing. This is because, especially in long discussions, a paragraph usually functions as part of a collective. The task of transitioning from one paragraph to the next is accomplished by different paragraph elements. The coherence between paragraphs is essential, irrespective of their structure. This is because it enhances the logical connection between ideas and, thus, facilitates the reader's understanding of the writer's concepts as presented in the essay. Therefore, it is crucial to consistently aim for a harmonious combination of inter-sentential connections inside a paragraph and smooth transitions between paragraphs.

Conclusion

Especially in academic settings, writing is a skill that requires instruction and cultivation. Effective writing is a crucial skill for achieving good communication through written media. This chapter has hitherto examined the details of exceptional writing abilities in a way that is easily understood by the average reader. We explored the definition of writing, the process of writing, and both general and specific strategies for effective writing. Acquiring proficient writing abilities necessitates dedicating a significant portion of time to engaging in diverse writing tasks. Repetitive practice is the key to achieving mastery; the most effective way to become a skilled writer is to persistently engage in writing. To enhance the likelihood of becoming exceptional and proficient writers, learners should integrate their writing skills with other beneficial ones.

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